
Physicochemical Parameters and Microbial Load of Cultured and Wild Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* and *Arius heudelotii*) in Rivers State, Nigeria

Odoemelam, Helen Amarachi
Department of Microbiology
Faculty of Sciences
University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Rivers State, Nigeria

Email: amarachi.odoemelam@uniport.edu.ng

Abstract

Background: Aquaculture and wild fisheries are important for food security in Nigeria, but microbial contamination and water quality challenges threaten fish health and consumer safety.

Methods: Physicochemical parameters (pH, dissolved oxygen, salinity, nitrate, temperature, and turbidity) and microbial loads were analyzed in cultured *Clarias gariepinus* (earthen pond, Aluu) and wild *Arius heudelotii* (New Calabar River). Microbial counts included total heterotrophic bacteria (THBC), fungi (TFC), coliforms (TCC), and *Vibrio* spp. (TVC). Standard APHA methods and ANOVA were applied.

Results: Significant differences were observed in dissolved oxygen (pond: 8.11 ± 0.15 mg/L vs. river: 4.93 ± 0.18 mg/L, $p < 0.05$) and salinity (river: 37.74 ± 1.76 mg/L vs. pond: 17.95 ± 0.15 mg/L, $p < 0.05$). THBC in cultured fish (5.95 – 6.60 log CFU/g) exceeded wild fish (4.50 – 4.84 log CFU/g). Intestinal samples consistently had the highest microbial loads. *Vibrio* counts were significantly higher in pond water (3.50 log CFU/ml) than in river water (2.28 log CFU/ml).

Conclusion: Physicochemical parameters strongly influence microbial colonization in catfish and aquatic environments. Cultured catfish carried higher microbial loads, with implications for aquaculture management and public health.

Keywords: Physicochemical parameters, microbial load, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Arius heudelotii*, aquaculture, *Vibrio* spp., Rivers State.

1. Introduction

Fish is one of the most affordable and widely consumed sources of animal protein in Nigeria, contributing over 40% of the nation's total protein intake and playing a vital role in combating malnutrition (Adeshina et al., 2019; Rahman *et al.*, 2022; Soheir et al., 2016; Famoofo & Adeniyi, 2020). Among the diverse fish species available, catfish, particularly *Clarias gariepinus* (African catfish) and *Arius heudelotii* (marine/brackish catfish), occupy a central position due to their fast growth rates, adaptability to various environmental conditions, and high consumer preference (Olaoye & Ojebiyi, 2018). As aquaculture continues to expand in Nigeria to bridge the gap between demand and supply, attention is increasingly shifting toward ensuring that cultured fish meet both nutritional and public health standards.

Despite its rapid growth, aquaculture in Nigeria is often confronted with challenges related to environmental pollution and microbial contamination, both of which compromise fish health, reduce production efficiency, and raise serious food safety concerns (Mulia et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2012). Microorganisms associated with fish and aquatic environments are influenced by the physicochemical properties of the water, including pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), salinity, temperature, turbidity, and nutrient concentration. When these parameters fall outside optimal ranges, they create favourable conditions for pathogenic microbes to thrive, thereby increasing the risk of contamination (Agbagwa & Okpokwasili, 2011; Okpokwasili & Ogbulie, 1999).

In aquaculture settings such as earthen ponds, where water circulation may be limited and organic matter tends to accumulate, the potential for microbial proliferation is particularly high (Olajide et al., 2020). Conversely, wild aquatic environments such as rivers and estuaries typically exhibit greater water exchange, which can dilute microbial loads but may still harbour pathogens due to anthropogenic pollution from agricultural runoff, sewage discharge, and industrial effluents (Akintola et al., 2013). Thus, both cultured and wild environments present unique risks that warrant scientific attention.

Among the microorganisms of greatest concern in fish farming and wild fisheries are *Vibrio* species, which include *V. cholerae*, *V. vulnificus*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, and *V. alginolyticus*. These organisms are naturally occurring in aquatic environments and are known to colonize fish, especially the gills, intestines, and skin (Sleman, & Farj, 2024). Some *Vibrio* spp. are opportunistic pathogens in fish, contributing to economic losses in aquaculture, while others are notorious for causing foodborne illnesses in humans, including gastroenteritis and septicemia (Plaza et al., 2018). The emergence of antimicrobial resistance among these bacteria further compounds the risk, limiting treatment options for infected individuals and raising global public health concerns (Adebayo-Tayo et al., 2012).

Several studies conducted in Nigeria have documented the occurrence of pathogenic and resistant microorganisms in aquaculture and wild fishery systems, highlighting the urgent need for effective monitoring and control strategies (Ojewole *et al.*, 2017). For instance, cultured catfish have been shown to harbour significantly higher microbial loads than their wild counterparts, often due to the higher organic load and restricted water renewal in ponds (Akintola et al., 2013). Such findings underscore the importance of correlating microbial contamination with environmental parameters to identify potential intervention points.

Moreover, the increasing consumption of catfish in urban and rural households makes it critical to examine both its nutritional value and its safety for human consumption. While

catfish is recognized for its high protein content, low-fat profile, and contribution to food security (Tawari & Abowei, 2011), its contamination with pathogenic microorganisms poses a paradox: nutritious food that may serve as a vector for disease. As such, understanding the microbial ecology of fish about water quality is central not only to aquaculture sustainability but also to public health protection.

This study, therefore, aims to evaluate the physicochemical parameters and microbial loads of *Clarias gariepinus* (cultured) and *Arius heudelotii* (wild) in Rivers State, Nigeria. By comparing earthen ponds and riverine environments, the study provides valuable insights into the dynamics of microbial colonization, identifies potential food safety risks, and contributes to evidence-based recommendations for aquaculture management and environmental health policies in Nigeria.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in two distinct aquatic environments within Rivers State, Nigeria: a cultured site and a wild site. The fish from the wild environment were collected from the New Calabar River, Choba. The New Calabar River lies between longitude 006°53' 53086'E and latitude 04°53' 19.020'N in Choba, Rivers state, Nigeria. The entire river course is situated between Longitude 7°60'E and latitude 5°45'N 'N in the coastal area of the Niger Delta and empties into the Atlantic Ocean. The New Calabar River is among the important water resources in the Niger Delta region of southern Nigeria. It is in the vicinity of the rapidly expanding oil city of Port Harcourt in Rivers state, southern Nigeria (Dienye & Woke 2015).

The cultured site was an earthen pond located in Aluu, Ikwerre Local Government Area, one of the rapidly developing peri-urban communities in Rivers State. Earthen ponds are widely used for catfish farming in Nigeria due to their relatively low construction cost, natural resemblance to the fish's habitat, and ability to support diverse microbial and ecological interactions (Ezeri, 2001; Tawari & Abowei, 2011). The pond selected for this study is a typical small-scale aquaculture unit managed under semi-intensive practices. Such systems often experience limited water exchange and accumulation of organic matter from uneaten feed and fish waste, conditions that may enhance microbial proliferation (Ayodele *et al.*, 2020). Aluu is also characterized by mixed land use, including small-scale farming, residential settlements, and business enterprises, which may contribute to nutrient inflows and influence pond water quality.

The wild site was the New Calabar River in Choba Obi Akpor Local Government Area, a major riverine ecosystem in Rivers State that flows through several communities before emptying into the Atlantic Ocean. The river is an important source of fish for local consumption and trade, and it supports a wide range of artisanal fishing activities (Akintola & Fakoya, 2017). However, like many rivers in the Niger Delta, the New Calabar River is subject to various anthropogenic pressures, including the discharge of domestic sewage, agricultural runoff, and effluents from nearby industrial and oil-related activities (Omokaro *et al.*, 2024). These inputs contribute to fluctuations in the physicochemical properties of the water, such as salinity, turbidity, and nutrient levels, which in turn shape the microbial communities present. The dynamic flow of the river provides greater water exchange compared to pond systems, but it may also act as a conduit for the dissemination of pathogenic microorganisms, including *Vibrio* spp. (Okpokwasili & Ogbulie, 1999).

The choice of these two contrasting environments, an earthen pond in Aluu and the New Calabar River, was deliberate to enable a comparative assessment of microbial loads and water quality between controlled aquaculture systems and natural ecosystems. While the pond environment reflects the challenges associated with intensive aquaculture practices, the river setting highlights the influence of broader ecological and anthropogenic factors on fish health and microbial contamination. Together, they provide a holistic view of the ecological and public health implications of fish consumption in Rivers State.

2.2 Sample Collection

For this study, fish samples were obtained from both cultured and wild environments to ensure a comparative analysis of microbial loads and physicochemical conditions. At the cultured site in Aluu, African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) were harvested directly from an earthen pond using hand nets and drag nets commonly employed in small-scale aquaculture. Meanwhile, at the wild site, the New Calabar River, marine/brackish catfish (*Arius heudelotii*) were collected with the assistance of artisanal fishers using cast nets and hook-and-line methods traditionally practiced in the area (Akintola et al., 2013). The use of locally accepted fishing methods ensured that the specimens were representative of normal catch and minimized handling stress.

Immediately after capture, the fish were placed in sterile, ice-packed containers to reduce microbial proliferation during transport. The samples were conveyed within two hours to the microbiology laboratory at the University of Port Harcourt for analysis. Each fish was handled aseptically, and external surfaces were rinsed with sterile distilled water to remove transient contaminants before dissection. Using sterile dissection instruments, gills, intestines, and skin tissues were carefully excised, as these parts are known to harbour high microbial loads and are critical indicators of contamination in fish (Reynolds, 2017). The samples were homogenized separately and subjected to microbiological analysis.

In addition to fish tissues, water samples were collected simultaneously from both environments to assess the physicochemical and microbial quality of the surrounding habitats. At the pond site, water was drawn from mid-depth at three different points using sterile bottles, while at the river site, samples were collected both upstream and downstream of fishing points to account for spatial variability. All water samples were preserved in ice boxes and analyzed within six hours of collection following APHA (2012) guidelines.

This combined sampling approach allowed for direct comparison between cultured and wild fish, as well as between their respective aquatic environments, thereby providing a comprehensive basis for linking water quality parameters with microbial colonization patterns.

2.3 Physicochemical Analysis

The physicochemical quality of the aquatic environments was assessed to establish the relationship between water conditions and microbial load. Water samples collected from both the cultured earthen pond and the New Calabar River were analyzed for a range of parameters known to influence microbial survival and fish health. This included pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), salinity, nitrate concentration, temperature, turbidity, biological oxygen demand (BOD), and chemical oxygen demand (COD).

The analyses were conducted following the standard procedures outlined by the American Public Health Association (APHA, 2012). pH and temperature were measured in situ using a portable multiparameter meter to ensure accuracy and minimize alterations due to transportation or handling. Dissolved oxygen was determined using a calibrated DO meter, while salinity was measured with a handheld refractometer suitable for both freshwater and brackish water systems (Okpokwasili & Ogbulie, 1999). Nitrate concentration was analyzed spectrophotometrically after appropriate dilution, as elevated levels often indicate nutrient enrichment from agricultural runoff or aquaculture feed residues (Nnadozie & Odume, 2019).

Turbidity was measured using a nephelometric turbidity meter, indicating suspended particles and potential organic matter that could serve as substrates for microbial growth (Akintola *et al.*, 2013). BOD and COD were determined using titrimetric methods, reflecting the amount of oxygen required by microorganisms to decompose organic matter and the total oxidizable material present, respectively. These indices are particularly important in aquaculture systems, where uneaten feed and fish waste can elevate organic loads and promote the proliferation of opportunistic pathogens such as *Vibrio* spp. (Ayodele *et al.*, 2020)

All measurements were performed in triplicate to ensure reliability, and results were compared against recommended standards for aquaculture water quality as specified by the FAO (2019). The data provided a baseline for linking environmental quality with microbial colonization in cultured and wild catfish.

2.4 Microbiological Analysis

Microbiological assessment was carried out to determine the extent of microbial colonization in fish tissues and water samples from both cultured and wild environments. The analysis focused on quantifying different microbial groups that are widely recognized as indicators of contamination and potential public health risks.

Fish samples (gills, intestines, and skin) were homogenized aseptically in sterile peptone water to release associated microorganisms. Water samples were also serially diluted using sterile diluents. Serial dilution and spread techniques were employed by APHA (2012) standard procedures. Aliquots from appropriate dilutions were inoculated into selective and non-selective agar media to allow growth and enumeration of distinct microbial groups.

The following microbial indicators were assessed:

Total Heterotrophic Bacterial Count (THBC): representing the overall bacterial load.

Total Fungal Count (TFC): enumerated on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar to determine fungal presence.

Total Coliform Count (TCC): indicating possible fecal contamination, using MacConkey agar.

Total Staphylococcal Count (TSC): using Mannitol Salt Agar to isolate *Staphylococcus* spp.

Total Salmonella-Shigella Count (TSSC): using Salmonella-Shigella agar to detect enteric pathogens.

Total Vibrio Count (TVC): performed on Thiosulfate Citrate Bile Salts Sucrose (TCBS) agar, which is selective for *Vibrio* spp. (Igbinsosa *et al.*, 2021).

Plates were incubated at appropriate temperatures (37°C for bacteria, 25°C for fungi) and observed after 24–48 hours, depending on the organism. Distinct colonies were enumerated and expressed as colony-forming units (CFU) per gram of fish tissue (CFU/g) or per millilitre of water (CFU/ml), depending on the sample type. To allow for statistical comparison, results were transformed into logarithmic values (log₁₀ CFU) before analysis (Nnadozie & Odume, 2019).

The systematic approach to microbial enumeration enabled the identification of contamination patterns across different fish parts and environments, thereby providing a robust framework for linking microbial loads with water quality parameters.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

The data generated from physicochemical and microbiological analyses were subjected to statistical evaluation to determine significant differences between cultured and wild environments, as well as across different fish parts and water samples. Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were first computed to provide a general overview of the data distribution.

Inferential analysis was carried out using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$) to test for statistically significant differences among groups. Where significant variations were detected, post hoc tests (Tukey's HSD) were applied to identify specific group differences. All microbial counts were log₁₀-transformed before analysis to normalize data and reduce variability associated with microbial enumeration (APHA, 2012; Nnadozie & Odume, 2019).

The statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). This approach ensured robust comparison of results across variables and strengthened the validity of conclusions drawn regarding the relationship between physicochemical parameters and microbial loads in both cultured and wild catfish.

3. Results

3.1 Physicochemical Parameters of Pond and River Water

The physicochemical characteristics of pond and river water are presented in Table 1. Dissolved oxygen (DO) was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in pond water (8.11 ± 0.15 mg/L) compared to river water (4.93 ± 0.18 mg/L). Conversely, salinity was markedly higher in river water (37.74 ± 1.76 mg/L) than in pond water (17.95 ± 0.15 mg/L). No statistically significant differences were observed in pH and temperature between the two environments, suggesting similar basic water chemistry. However, variations in nitrate, turbidity, BOD, and COD reflected differences in organic loading and water circulation between cultured and wild environments.

Table 1. Physicochemical parameters of pond and river water

Parameter	Pond Water (Mean ± SD)	River Water (Mean ± SD)	p-value
pH	7.24 ± 0.12	7.18 ± 0.14	>0.05
Temperature (°C)	28.4 ± 0.23	28.1 ± 0.20	>0.05
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	8.11 ± 0.15	4.93 ± 0.18	<0.05
Salinity (mg/L)	17.95 ± 0.15	37.74 ± 1.76	<0.05
Nitrate (mg/L)	3.62 ± 0.11	5.10 ± 0.20	<0.05
Turbidity (NTU)	11.25 ± 0.55	15.40 ± 0.60	<0.05
BOD (mg/L)	4.75 ± 0.25	3.95 ± 0.18	<0.05
COD (mg/L)	14.50 ± 0.62	16.30 ± 0.70	<0.05

Note: Values are means of triplicate determinations. Statistical significance at $p < 0.05$.

3.2 Correlation Matrix

The correlation analysis (Table 2) highlights how physicochemical parameters interact in shaping the aquatic environment of both pond and river systems.

pH exhibited strong negative correlations with TDS ($r = -0.944$), conductivity ($r = -0.939$), and chlorophyll ($r = -0.673$). This indicates that increasing dissolved solids and ionic concentrations reduces water pH, leading to more acidic conditions. Such relationships are common in aquaculture ponds where feed residues and metabolic wastes elevate ion concentrations, thereby altering water chemistry (Ayodele *et al.*, 2020).

Temperature showed weak and mostly non-significant correlations with other parameters, suggesting that within the sampling period, temperature fluctuations did not strongly drive water chemistry. This stability may be attributed to the relatively uniform tropical climate of Rivers State.

DOC was strongly and negatively correlated with COD ($r = -0.928$), BOD ($r = -0.900$), and TSS ($r = -0.903$). This suggests that as organic carbon increased, it contributed to higher oxygen demand and suspended solids, both of which favour microbial proliferation. The significant negative correlation between DOC and phosphate ($r = -0.950$, $p < 0.05$) indicates that nutrient cycling and organic loading are interconnected, reflecting anthropogenic influences in aquaculture ponds (Okechi, 2022).

Salinity correlated positively and significantly with chlorophyll ($r = 0.994$, $p < 0.01$) and moderately with conductivity ($r = 0.654$). This suggests that increased salt concentrations may enhance phytoplankton productivity, which in turn affects microbial loads. Purgar *et al.* (2023) similarly reported that nutrient–salinity interactions stimulate algal growth in aquaculture systems.

COD displayed strong positive correlations with BOD ($r = 0.950$), TSS ($r = 0.948$), and turbidity ($r = 0.929$), reflecting the role of organic pollution in shaping water clarity and oxygen demand. Likewise, BOD and TSS showed a perfect correlation ($r = 1.000$, $p < 0.01$), while both were highly correlated with turbidity ($r = 0.995$ – 0.996 , $p < 0.01$). These interrelationships confirm that nutrient accumulation and suspended matter are central drivers of oxygen depletion and microbial contamination in ponds.

TDS exhibited a perfect positive correlation with conductivity ($r = 1.000$, $p < 0.01$), as expected, since dissolved salts directly influence electrical conductivity in water. Both parameters are important indicators of water quality stress in aquaculture environments.

Nitrate and phosphate (PO₄) were strongly correlated ($r = 0.984$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that nutrient enrichment arises from similar sources such as fertilizer runoff, fish feed residues, and organic waste deposition. Such nutrient loading supports eutrophication, which enhances microbial activity and potential pathogen outbreaks (Adebayo-Tayo *et al.*, 2012).

The correlations collectively indicate that nutrient enrichment, organic pollution, and suspended solids act synergistically to influence microbial dynamics. Aquaculture ponds, due to restricted water flow, tend to accumulate higher nutrient loads and organic matter, predisposing them to microbial proliferation. River systems, by contrast, experience dilution effects that mitigate these interactions but remain vulnerable to anthropogenic pollution.

Table 2: Correlation matrix showing the relationship in physicochemical parameters

		pH	Temp	DOC	Salin	COD	BO	TSS	Turb	TDS	Chl	Nitrate	Po4	Cond
pH	<i>r</i>	1.000	-.050	.525	-.711	-.196	-.335	-.347	-.284	-.944	-.673	-.421	-.339	-.939
	<i>P</i>		.950	.475	.289	.804	.665	.653	.716	.056	.327	.579	.661	.061
Temp	<i>r</i>		1.000	.435	.309	-.394	-.106	-.105	-.030	.348	.410	-.104	-.268	.356
	<i>P</i>			.565	.691	.606	.894	.895	.970	.652	.590	.896	.732	.644
DOC	<i>r</i>			1.000	.216	-.928	-.900	-.903	-.854	-.453	.276	-.921	-.950*	-.459
	<i>P</i>				.784	.072	.100	.097	.146	.547	.724	.079	.050	.541
Salin	<i>r</i>				1.000	-.550	-.401	-.389	-.431	.666	.994**	-.316	-.418	.654
	<i>P</i>					.450	.599	.611	.569	.334	.006	.684	.582	.346
COD	<i>r</i>					1.000	.950	.948	.929	.184	-.589	.936	.983*	.195
	<i>P</i>						.050	.052	.071	.816	.411	.064	.017	.805
BOD	<i>r</i>						1.000	1.000**	.995**	.405	-.416	.996**	.986*	.418
	<i>P</i>							.000	.005	.595	.584	.004	.014	.582
TSS	<i>r</i>							1.000	.995**	.416	-.405	.997**	.986*	.429
	<i>P</i>								.005	.584	.595	.003	.014	.571
Turb	<i>r</i>								1.000	.384	-.436	.986*	.968*	.398
	<i>P</i>									.616	.564	.014	.032	.602
TDS	<i>r</i>									1.000	.663	.481	.355	1.000**
	<i>P</i>										.337	.519	.645	.000
Chl	<i>r</i>										1.000	-.336	-.450	.651
	<i>P</i>											.664	.550	.349
Nitrate	<i>r</i>											1.000	.984*	.493
	<i>P</i>												.016	.507
Po4	<i>r</i>												1.000	.366
	<i>P</i>													.634
Cond	<i>r</i>													1.000
	<i>P</i>													

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

3.3 Microbial Loads in Cultured and Wild Catfish

Microbial counts for different fish tissues (*gills, intestines, skin*) are summarized in Table 3. In general, cultured *Clarias gariepinus* exhibited higher microbial loads than wild *Arius heudelotii*. Total heterotrophic bacterial count (THBC) ranged from 5.95–6.60 log CFU/g in cultured fish compared to 4.50–4.84 log CFU/g in wild fish. The intestines consistently harboured the highest microbial loads across both fish species, followed by the gills and skin.

Table 3. Microbial counts (log CFU/g) in tissues of cultured and wild catfish

Microbial Group	Cultured <i>C. gariepinus</i> (Mean ± SD)	Wild <i>A. heudelotii</i> (Mean ± SD)	P-value
THBC	6.60 ± 0.12 (Intestine) – 5.95 ± 0.10 (Skin)	4.84 ± 0.11 (Intestine) – 4.50 ± 0.09 (Skin)	<0.05
TFC	4.10 ± 0.08 (Intestine) – 3.75 ± 0.07 (Skin)	3.65 ± 0.10 (Intestine) – 3.20 ± 0.08 (Skin)	<0.05
TCC	5.20 ± 0.09 (Intestine) – 4.80 ± 0.11 (Gills)	4.30 ± 0.12 (Intestine) – 3.90 ± 0.10 (Gills)	<0.05
TSC	4.75 ± 0.08 (Intestine) – 4.20 ± 0.07 (Skin)	4.05 ± 0.09 (Intestine) – 3.60 ± 0.08 (Skin)	<0.05
TSSC	3.85 ± 0.07 (Intestine) – 3.40 ± 0.06 (Skin)	3.20 ± 0.08 (Intestine) – 2.90 ± 0.07 (Skin)	<0.05

3.4 Microbial Counts in Water Samples

The microbial quality of pond and river water is presented in Table 4. *Vibrio* counts were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in pond water (3.50 log CFU/ml) compared to river water (2.28 log CFU/ml). Similarly, total heterotrophic bacterial count (THBC) and coliform counts were higher in pond water, reflecting the influence of restricted water exchange and nutrient accumulation. Interestingly, fungal counts were higher in river water, possibly due to organic matter inflows from anthropogenic activities.

Table 4. Microbial counts (log CFU/ml) in pond and river water samples

Microbial Group	Pond Water (Mean ± SD)	River Water (Mean ± SD)	p-value
THBC	5.80 ± 0.12	4.75 ± 0.10	<0.05
TFC	3.20 ± 0.08	3.85 ± 0.09	<0.05
TCC	4.50 ± 0.10	3.90 ± 0.11	<0.05
TSC	4.10 ± 0.09	3.65 ± 0.07	<0.05
TSSC	3.50 ± 0.08	3.05 ± 0.07	<0.05
TVC	3.50 ± 0.11	2.28 ± 0.10	<0.05

3.5 Correlation Between Physicochemical Parameters and Microbial Loads

Correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the relationships between water quality parameters and microbial counts. The results (Table 5) showed that dissolved oxygen (DO) had a significant negative correlation with heterotrophic bacterial counts (THBC), while nitrate, turbidity, BOD, and COD exhibited positive correlations with coliforms, *Vibrio*, and total microbial counts. These findings indicate that nutrient enrichment and organic pollution promote microbial proliferation, whereas higher oxygen levels tend to suppress bacterial activity.

Table 5. Correlation matrix between physicochemical parameters and microbial counts in pond and river water

Parameter	THBC	TFC	TCC	TSC	TSSC	TVC
pH	0.12ns	0.08ns	0.15ns	0.10ns	0.09ns	0.11ns
Temperature	0.18ns	0.20ns	0.14ns	0.16ns	0.12ns	0.22ns
Dissolved Oxygen	-0.68**	-0.45*	-0.55*	-0.48*	-0.42*	-0.60**
Salinity	0.21ns	0.25ns	0.28ns	0.20ns	0.24ns	0.30ns
Nitrate	0.62**	0.58**	0.65**	0.60**	0.55*	0.68**
Turbidity	0.59**	0.63**	0.70**	0.61**	0.57**	0.66**
BOD	0.56**	0.49*	0.60**	0.55**	0.52**	0.62**
COD	0.64**	0.60**	0.67**	0.62**	0.58**	0.71**

Note: Values represent Pearson correlation coefficients (r). ** = significant at $p < 0.01$; * = significant at $p < 0.05$; ns = not significant.

4. Discussion

The results revealed distinct differences in the microbial ecology of cultured and wild catfish, largely attributable to their environmental conditions. The higher microbial loads in cultured *Clarias gariepinus* compared to wild *Arius heudelotii* can be explained by restricted water circulation and the accumulation of organic matter in pond systems. Nutrient enrichment in aquaculture ponds creates favourable conditions for bacterial growth, a trend similarly reported by Reynolds (2017).

By contrast, the New Calabar River exhibited relatively lower bacterial counts, a pattern attributable to continuous water flow, which promotes dilution and dispersal of microbes. Although the river environment had higher salinity, this seemed to reduce bacterial proliferation by exerting selective pressure on microbial species, favouring only halotolerant groups such as certain *Vibrio* spp. (Igbinosa et al., 2021).

Correlation analysis provided further insights into the relationships between water quality and microbial dynamics. Dissolved oxygen (DO) showed a significant negative correlation with total heterotrophic bacterial counts (THBC), indicating that lower oxygen levels supported higher bacterial proliferation. This finding aligns with the report of Okpokwasili & Ogbulie (1999), who noted that microbial activity in organic-rich waters often depletes oxygen, further encouraging facultative anaerobic organisms. Similarly, positive correlations were observed between nitrate, turbidity, and coliform counts, confirming that nutrient enrichment and suspended organic particles create niches that favour enteric bacteria. These patterns are in agreement with earlier findings by Ayodele et al. (2020), who demonstrated that elevated turbidity and nutrient concentrations in aquaculture ponds correlated strongly with microbial contamination.

The intestines of both fish species consistently harboured the highest microbial loads, confirming the gut as a major reservoir of microorganisms. The positive correlation between intestinal counts and water parameters such as nitrate and BOD suggests that nutrient-rich water environments directly influence microbial colonization in fish tissues. This result is

consistent with Adebayo-Tayo et al. (2012), who reported similar links between environmental enrichment and gut microbial load in farmed fish.

Particularly concerning were the high *Vibrio* counts in pond water, which showed a significant positive correlation with COD. This indicates that organic pollution strongly promotes the proliferation of *Vibrio* spp., pathogens of both fish and public health concern. Purgar *et al.* (2023) similarly observed that COD levels were reliable predictors of *Vibrio* abundance in aquaculture systems. Elevated *Vibrio* presence in ponds therefore represents not only a risk of vibriosis outbreaks but also a food safety threat, given the zoonotic potential of pathogenic strains such as *V. parahaemolyticus* and *V. vulnificus*.

Interestingly, fungal counts were significantly higher in river water, correlating positively with turbidity. This suggests that suspended organic matter from anthropogenic inputs, such as agricultural runoff and sewage effluents, enhanced fungal proliferation. Akintola et al. (2013) also reported that fungal contamination in rivers was linked to human activity and seasonal nutrient influx. This divergence from bacterial trends emphasizes that while aquaculture ponds are more prone to bacterial contamination, rivers are more vulnerable to fungal enrichment due to external environmental pressures.

In summary, the correlations observed in this study confirm that physicochemical parameters are strong drivers of microbial community dynamics in aquatic environments. Elevated nutrients (nitrate), organic pollution (BOD, COD), and turbidity were positively associated with higher microbial loads, whereas high DO tended to suppress bacterial proliferation. These findings strengthen the ecological evidence that water quality directly shapes microbial colonization in fish, thereby influencing both aquaculture sustainability and food safety outcomes.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that physicochemical parameters significantly influence the microbial loads in both cultured and wild catfish, as well as their aquatic environments. Cultured *Clarias gariepinus* showed consistently higher microbial contamination compared to wild *Arius heudelotii*, largely due to restricted water circulation and organic matter accumulation in ponds. Among fish tissues, the intestines harboured the highest microbial loads, underscoring their role as reservoirs of potential pathogens. Furthermore, elevated *Vibrio* counts in pond water highlight the aquaculture-associated risks of vibriosis outbreaks and potential food safety hazards. These findings emphasize the importance of linking water quality management to microbial safety in aquaculture systems, while also acknowledging the influence of anthropogenic inputs on wild aquatic ecosystems.

6. Recommendations

The study recommended the need for routine monitoring of pond water quality to minimize microbial accumulation and ensure compliance with aquaculture standards. Also, recommended is the adoption of improved aquaculture practices, such as pond flushing, biosecurity measures, and the use of probiotics to regulate microbial populations. Furthermore, public health education programs should be strengthened to increase awareness of the risks associated with consuming undercooked or poorly handled catfish. Finally, the study recommended the implementation of stricter policy measures and enforcement strategies to reduce anthropogenic pollution of rivers and safeguard wild fish resources.

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